

Department of
Economics

UNIVERSITY OF
BATH

Country Report: Japan

(ES12002: Coursework)

*Jack Desveaux, Charlie Henderson, Jacob Herrmann, Sanjit Kataksham, Ed
Smith*

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Japan is a nation with a very unique economy. It was the first Asian nation to industrialise, and grew at breakneck speed to become a developed country after the second world war. But it has now been stagnant for three decades, with negligible growth in wages or per-person output. And it is one of the first places in the world to truly feel the effects of the ‘silver tsunami’ – an ageing and shrinking population. This report will discuss the current state of Japan and its economy, the effects of the 2008 financial crisis and COVID-19, how its government has responded to these shocks, and the growing impacts of Japan’s demographic challenges on the economy.

The Macroeconomy of Japan

Source: (Japan Map 360°, 2024)

Japan is an island nation in eastern Asia with a population of around 123,000,000 (Worldometers, 2024), neighbouring Korea, China and Russia.

As noted by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Japan (2019), the islands are very prone to natural disasters, including typhoons, earthquakes and tsunamis, which can have large effects on the economy. Spending on disaster

prevention and response was ¥2.9 trillion in 1993 alone.

The Japanese islands are very poor in natural resources – Japan is the world’s largest natural gas importer and the second-largest importer of oil, as it has virtually no natural energy resources. It also lacks most useful metals and minerals. The main resource Japan does have in abundance is fish, due to its large coastline (Owuor, 2019).

The modern Japanese economy began with the Meiji Restoration in the mid-19th century. This brought a new government to power, which looked to Westernise the country and economy (Britannica, 2020). Workers could now choose their own profession, model factories were constructed as an example to entrepreneurs, and 2500km of railroad were laid by the mid-1890s (Goto-Jones, 2009, p.56). Mandatory education was also implemented (Ito, 1992). Combined, these measures spurred rapid growth in the quantity of physical capital (machinery and infrastructure) and human capital (human skill and education) and allowed Japan to become the first non-Western

industrial nation. However, much of this progress was destroyed in the Second World War.

Following the war, the economy began to rebound after only a few years, stimulated by war procurements from the Korean war. GNP (output produced in an economy in a year, including output produced by foreign citizens overseas) increased 250% by the mid-1950s (Goto-Jones, 2009, p.98). The industrial sector continued this rapid growth, and GNP tripled over the 1960s (Goto-Jones, 2009, pp.102-103). By the end of this boom period in the mid-1990s, Japan's output was 10 times the level of 1950 (Yoshikawa, 2021, p.154). However, years of stagnation have followed, which will be discussed later in the report.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Source: University of Groningen (2018)

The contemporary Japanese economy is now the world's 4th largest, with a real GDP (a similar measure of output, 'real' meaning adjusted for inflation) of USD 5 trillion in 2019. As shown on figure 1, GDP expanded rapidly from 1950 to the mid-1990s, but growth has trended downwards, and output is now relatively stagnant. Figure 2 shows this is also the case for GDP per capita (per person), which hasn't kept up with the average of the Group of 7 (G7) advanced economies in that period.

One important reason is Japan's demographic challenges. It had a very high life expectancy of 84.5 years at birth in 2021 (World Health Organization (WHO), 2020), but a very low birth rate of 6.9 births per 1000 people in 2024 (CIA, 2023). This means as people age there are fewer younger workers to support their healthcare and retirement, increasing the burden of social services on younger generations and shrinking the overall labour force.

Figure 3 – Sectors as a % of GDP. Source: Statistics Japan (2021)

Another reason for low growth is Japan’s service-based economy. The transition towards service-sector employment has been occurring for decades - figure 3 shows the share of output produced in the tertiary (services) sector has surged since 1950 to 73.1%, and the share produced in the primary sector (farming, mining etc.) has fallen to only 1%. As growth in productivity (output per hour of work) has been much slower in the service sector in recent years (Fukao, 2010), annual wage growth has stalled, as shown in figure 4. Whilst there have been some fluctuations, annual wages are essentially unchanged since 1990, and are still trending downwards despite the shrinking labour force. This is despite Japan’s unemployment rate (the proportion of the labour force unable to find work) being, if anything, too low – it was 2.6% in May 2024 (OECD, 2024c), and has been low for many years. This has resulted in a consistently tight labour market, which will be discussed later in the report.

Figure 4 – Source: University of Groningen (2018)

Japan’s high national debt is also related to the ageing population. In 2022, Japan was the most heavily indebted government in the world, with central government debt of 214% of GDP. The G7 mean was only 90% of GDP (International Monetary Fund (IMF), 2024). This is shown in figure 5 below – Japan’s indebtedness was comparable to other G7 nations in the 1990s, but has risen much more rapidly in the following decades.

Figure 5 – Source: IMF (2024)

The ageing population has forced higher government spending, particularly on social security. As the population ages, increasing funds must be allocated to pensions and healthcare for the elderly, and low growth means output has not kept pace with these increases. Figure 6 shows how social security spending has risen in recent decades – it is currently more than a quarter of total output. Figure 7 displays the cause - rising public sector health spending, and especially old age spending (spending on pensions etc.), which since 1980 to 8.9% of GDP.

Figure 6

Figure 7

Source: National Institute of Population and Social Security Research (IPSS)(2021)

It would be expected that labour market engagement would fall due to demographic challenges - nevertheless, the proportion of the population engaged in the labour market in Japan (shown in figure 8) has not fallen, but risen over recent years. This does not reflect a rise in the overall supply of labour, however - figure 9 shows the proportion of those working employed in part-time work rose from 11.1% to 24.8%, counteracting the rise in engagement.

Figure 8 – Source: University of Groningen (2018)

Figure 9 – Source: OECD (2024b)

Figure 10 – Source: OECD (2024b)

With economic stagnation, Japan has struggled with extremely low inflation (the rate of increase in prices), often deflation, for a number of years, as shown in figure 10. Whilst Japan’s inflation rate was above the G7 mean in the 1970s, it fell as the economy stagnated, and has been largely below the G7 average for decades. This is despite the best efforts of the Bank of Japan (BOJ), which has been trying to stimulate the economy with low interest rates. Whilst Japan is not the only developed country to have suffered stubbornly low inflation lately (the G7 mean has also been low), it has been the most severely impacted.

However, Japan has recently been able to raise inflation to a normal level close to its 2% target, but still below other G7 countries, as shown in figure 11. Time will tell whether this represents the eventual success of the BOJ, or if the economy will slide back into deflation in coming years.

Figure 11 – Source: OECD (2024b)

Japan has enjoyed a sizeable current account surplus (a measure of net income) for the past 30 years, illustrated in figure 12 with a breakdown of its components. Part of the reason for this is Japan’s strong industrial export industry, especially in machinery, vehicles and chemicals (Observatory of Economic Complexity, 2022). In recent years, however, net trade (exports minus imports) of goods has declined, falling into deficit in 2011. As depicted in figure 13, this is largely due to growth in Japan’s goods imports, instead of a fall in exports. A depreciation (fall in value) of the Yen (BOJ, 2014) reduced the quantity of foreign currency one Yen could be exchanged for, increasing the price of imported goods in Yen, thus raising the value of imports. In recent years, high raw material prices have widened the deficit again as Japan relies on importing most of the raw materials they use (BOJ, 2023).

However, the current account surplus has been sustained by high primary income (the net flow of profits, investment earnings etc.), especially in the 2020s. This is because of growth in direct investment income that Japanese companies receive from manufacturing outsourced abroad (Ministry of Finance Japan (MOF), 2024).

Figure 12 – Source: MOF (2024)

Figure 13 – Source: MOF (2024)

The 2008 Financial Crisis

The 2008 financial crisis is one of the major recent economic shocks Japan has experienced. While the US and many Western European countries experienced major bank failures, Japan's financial system was resilient. Japanese banks were largely unaffected by the financial crisis because they didn't have many of the toxic assets (mortgage-backed securities) that were the cause of the crisis in their portfolios. However, Japan still suffered a severe recession (two quarters of negative GDP growth), as shown in the excerpt from figure 1 below, with real GDP falling by 5.6% in 2008-2009. This was due to the impact of falling exports. By 2007, the value of exports of goods and services was 17.3% of Japan's GDP (World Bank Open Data, 2024), and Japanese companies were reliant on exporting due to low domestic demand. However, the financial crisis led to rising unemployment and uncertainty in Japan's largest export markets such as the US. Consumers postponed the purchase of non-necessities like cars and electrical appliances and these products are some of Japan's main exports, so exports fell by 12.5% in 2008 alone (Kawai and Takagi, 2009).

Figure 1 (excerpt) – Source: University of Groningen (2019)

This sharp drop in exports had a serious impact on Japan's economy, as it lowered net trade. Net trade is a component of aggregate demand (AD, total demand for goods and services in an economy) given by the equation:

$$AD = c_0 + c_1(1 - \tau)Y + I(r) + G + X - mY$$

where

$c_0 = \text{autonomous consumption}$

$c_1 = \text{Marginal Propensity to Consume}$

$\tau = \text{income tax rate}$

$I(r) = \text{Investment (a function of interest rate } r)$

$G = \text{Government spending}$

$m = \text{Marginal Propensity to Import}$

$X = \text{Export Revenue}$

Thus, a fall in net trade ($X - mY$) will lower AD. An illustration of the impact this had on the wider economy can be seen in diagram 1 below. This plots aggregate demand (initially AD_0) against real output. The level of output will be given by the point at which the AD curve and the 45° line output = AD meet, as this is the point at which all goods and services the economy produces are purchased. The fall in net trade means aggregate demand falls from AD_0 to AD_1 , as autonomous demand (aggregate demand dependent on factors unrelated to the Japanese economy) decreases, because export demand is determined by external elements like incomes in other countries. Thus, output will also fall from Y_0 to Y_1 , causing the fall in GDP during the crisis.

Diagram 1 – Aggregate Demand in 2008 Financial Crisis

In response to the fall in real GDP, the BOJ reduced the policy interest rate (the rate offered by the central bank) from 0.75% to 0.3% between 2007 and 2008 (BOJ, 2009). Theoretically, reducing the policy rate should have led to an increase in aggregate demand as investment is a function of interest rates. When the interest rate is lower, consumers will receive lower interest payments from saving income, encouraging them to spend instead, increasing consumption. Furthermore, interest rates on loans will also decrease, lowering the cost of borrowing for firms to invest in their business and thus raising investment. Consumption and investment are significant components of aggregate demand, so AD should have risen after the interest rate reduction - however, in reality, this did not occur. Japan's real GDP didn't recover to pre-crisis levels until 2013, according to the World Bank (World Bank Open Data, 2024). This is largely due to low consumer confidence in the Japanese economy - in 2008, Japan's consumer confidence was at the lowest level in 7 years (OECD, 2024a). Unemployment rose by 1.1% between 2008 and 2009, reaching 5.1% (OECD, 2024b). As a result, workers had lower job security and so saved more in case they lost their income, offsetting the fall in interest rates.

Nevertheless, because the policy rate was already low, the 0.45% reduction was expected to have little effect. Therefore, the government stepped in with expansionary fiscal policy, cutting taxes such as income tax. This expansionary fiscal policy included \$40 billion in cuts to income tax (Katada, 2013). However, due to the aforementioned low consumer confidence in Japan the marginal propensity to consume (MPC, the proportion of additional income spent on consumption) was very low. Households preferred to save the extra income they had from the tax cuts, rather than raising consumption spending. The low MPC relates to the concept of the multiplier, as is part of the formula for the multiplier, shown below:

$$\frac{1}{1 - c_1(1 - \tau) + m}$$

The multiplier determines the overall impact of money entering the circular flow of spending on final GDP. When spending on goods and services increases, this increase becomes profits for businesses and wages for workers. These businesses or workers will then spend some of this additional income on goods and services, continuing the cycle. Thus, if the MPC is low, only a small proportion of the government's stimulus package will be spent by the recipients, resulting in a low multiplier (as $c_1 = MPC$) and a low overall rise in output.

Diagram 2 – Impact of Government Intervention

The increase in government spending in the fiscal stimulus causes aggregate demand to increase from AD_1 to AD_2 , illustrated on diagram 2. However, the low multiplier reduces the gradient of the curve (hence AD_2 being less steep), meaning that although AD has increased it does not reach the pre-financial crisis level of AD_0 . As such, post-stimulus output would be at Y_2 – an improvement, but still significantly below the pre-crisis level. This is supported by the excerpt of figure 1, with the GDP growth rate in 2009-2010 (4.5%) not compensating for the fall in GDP in prior years. The failure of expansionary fiscal and monetary policy to raise demand back to 2007 levels is why Japan's real GDP struggled to recover after the financial crisis. Even after 2013, Japan's economic growth has remained sluggish.

The COVID-19 Pandemic

The coronavirus pandemic is the second major economic shock to be discussed. Japan was not affected as badly by the virus itself as many other developed economies, and did not have to impose a national lockdown. However, Japan's economy still took a big hit, with the IMF estimating a 4.5% reduction in GDP in 2020 (Tsigaris, Teixeira and Honma, 2024), mainly due to the fall in exports of 11.1% (Kyodo News, 2021). This is due to a fall in demand from abroad due to global uncertainty and COVID restrictions in other countries, and stricter sanitary and travel regulations making trade more difficult. The impact of this on output is shown on diagram 3, showing AD and output as in diagrams 1 and 2. A fall in exports lowers demand from AD_0 to AD_1 as autonomous demand decreases, thus lowering equilibrium output from Y_0 to Y_1 . Additionally, unemployment rose by 0.4% (Tsigaris, Teixeira and Honma, 2024) due to lower demand in the tourism and transport industries.

Diagram 3 – Impact of COVID-19 on Aggregate Demand

In response to COVID, the Japanese government once again resorted to extensive expansionary fiscal policy, as the BOJ had limited scope for monetary policy due to long-term interest rates already being low or negative (OECD, 2024b). The government focused its efforts on expenditure, with COVID-related payment packages estimated at \$3 trillion in 2020 (BBC News, 2020) - 60% of Japan's economy at the time - across 3 rounds of spending, to try and stimulate the economy. The first two rounds allowed the economy to rebound in the third quarter of 2020 with 5.3% GDP growth following the 8.2% shrinkage in the second quarter (BBC News, 2020). This is because the government made direct payments to households and small businesses, allowing them

to consume and invest more. However, due to lacking consumer confidence in the economy following 30 years of economic stagnation, and a global pandemic, the MPC was very low. This would cause the multiplier to fall to as a lower MPC would result in a larger denominator for the multiplier, meaning it is smaller. The fall in the tax rate would have had the reverse effect however in this instance, the effect of the falling MPC dominated the falling tax in Japan. This results in the flatter gradient of the blue curve in diagram 4 below. This means the increase in output was much smaller than the \$3 trillion increase in government expenditure into the economy.

Diagram 4 – Impact of Stimulus

The diagram above shows the increase in autonomous demand, mainly coming from the increase in government spending, from the initial curve to the other two curves as they have a higher y intercept. Overall, we can see that if the MPC and thus the multiplier had remained constant, the government intervention would have seen AD rise from AD1 to AD2, with output rising from Y1 to Y2. However, we know that the Japanese economy did not experience booming economic growth following the pandemic, which must be due to the lower MPC caused by lacking confidence, leading to the shallower gradient of the blue curve, resulting in a reduced output of Y3 and demand at AD3.

The low impact of the stimulus meant the economy did not begin a period of high economic growth - instead, the increase in spending has caused GDP to return to stagnant pre-pandemic levels. It is also worth considering that a major focus of the third round of government spending was investing in green technologies and digital

development through subsidisation (BBC News, 2020). As such, it is likely that many benefits of this spending are realised in the long run, as these markets are still emerging, and need time to properly develop. These developing industries may help Japan boost its rate of GDP growth long-term to overcome their current period of stagnation, by raising productivity through creating new jobs in fast-growing sectors.

Demographic Challenges and an Ageing Population

The largest long-term macroeconomic issue affecting Japan is its demographic shift caused by an ageing population - this has been holding back the nation's economy for years, and is set to continue to do so. At the most basic level, it is the result of Japan's very high life expectancy of 84.5 years (WHO, 2020), and very low birth rate of 6.9 births per 1000 people (CIA, 2023). There are many possible causes for this low birth rate – one is the division of childcare responsibilities, because Japanese culture places most of the child caring responsibility on women, making it harder for them to balance having children with other commitments (D'Ambrogio, 2020). Compounding the ageing population is Japan's low immigration flows which, unlike in many other developed nations with low birth rates, means there isn't an influx of young workers to maintain the labour force. Japan achieved only 3% of its immigration quota in 2019 despite a new policy that aimed to encourage immigration (Saito, 2024).

Diagram 5 – Efficiency Wage Model

One of the main issues generated by the ageing population is a small and shrinking workforce, as fewer people are willing and able to work. The efficiency wage model in diagram 5 shows this. In this model, the wage-setting curve is upward-sloping as the amount of effort workers will exert for a given wage falls as the employment rate rises, as it becomes easier for workers to find a new job should they lose their current one. As such, they will exert less effort at each wage.

Diagram 6 – Best Response Curves

One way to illustrate this is with a model of a worker's best response curve. This partially determines the wage setting curve, along with the firm's cost of production. Essentially, as unemployment is exceedingly low, Japanese workers do not expect to be unemployed for long if they lose their job, as vacancies are high so a new job should be easy to find. This means their employment rent, which is the worker's net benefit from being employed, is low. Because of this, each Japanese worker values their job less than in otherwise comparable example country A, represented by the lower best response curve for Japanese workers on diagram 6. At a wage such as W_1 , whilst a worker in another country might exert effort E_A , a Japanese worker will exert much lower effort E_J , leading to lower productivity of Japanese labour. This leads to a much higher cost per unit of effort for firms in Japan, and so a steeper wage-setting curve.

The equilibrium point (where wages and unemployment are stable) will be the wage paid that allows for the firm to achieve the best level of productivity from its workers. As such, the point E1 represents the level of employment currently in the economy, whilst the difference between the labour force and E1 is the level of unemployment in the economy. This leads to an equilibrium at point A, where a real wage is paid according to the wage setting curve. At this point there is a markup which is shown on diagram 6, this is difference between the average product of each worker (the revenue per unit of output) and the wage paid. It essentially represents the profit of the firm, and the firm wants to keep this constant.

Following an increase in demand for labour in Japan, for example in care services, firms will want to increase output and will therefore have to hire more workers, decreasing unemployment. This will move employment from E1 to E2. However, since this is so close to the labour force cap (the maximum possible level of employment, with a 0% unemployment rate), a significant wage increase will have to be provided such that the workers hired will exert the same level of effort. Workers will have bargaining power to demand a higher wage as they can easily find another job, and competition for workers between firms will increase.

However, because the wage increase required is so significant (moving the real wage to point C), Japanese firms will not be able to provide this increase and maintain their current markup, without increasing prices significantly and angering consumers. Therefore, because of the tightness of the labour market (high numbers of vacancies but low unemployment to fill them), Japanese firms will remain unresponsive to changes in demand and will not be able to significantly increase output when needed.

Among other issues, this tight labour market has the potential to decrease Japan's ability to export. As the cost of labour in Japan increases as described above, costs will also rise for Japanese businesses, leading to high costs of production compared to other nations. This will mean Japanese firms will have to charge higher prices for exports to maintain their markup, and thus will struggle to compete with cheaper

alternatives. The result would be a decline in Japan’s historically strong exports (this fall in goods exports can be seen since 2010 in figure 13, repeated below).

Figure 13 (repeated) – Source: MOF (2024)

This may result in significant challenges for the economy as Japan has struggled with low aggregate demand domestically for years as previously discussed, a problem which will only grow as the population (and thus size of the Japanese market) shrinks. Exports can compensate for poor domestic demand to some extent, but if exports are also falling, it will be hard for the government to prevent economic contraction.

Falling exports could also lead to a depreciation (fall in value) of the Japanese Yen. This is because the demand for Yen is created when foreign buyers wish to purchase goods or services from Japanese firms – essentially, from exports. A fall in exports will lead to a fall in the number of buyers wishing to exchange other currencies for Yen, and so a fall in the Yen’s value. As the Yen is less valuable, the price of foreign goods in Yen will thus rise, resulting in higher import prices for Japanese consumers, lowering quality of life. Higher import prices will also further increase the costs of production for firms, as Japan’s natural scarcity of raw materials means they rely on imports.

Another way in which the demographic changes in Japan are impacting its economy is in terms of government budgeting. Whilst the pool of available taxpayers in Japan is decreasing as the workforce shrinks, a rising elderly population means the need for healthcare and pensions spending is constantly increasing, as previously discussed. Figure 7 illustrates this, and is repeated below. The government is therefore less able to utilise fiscal policy to impact the economy without taking on large debts and thus

creating future fiscal problems. This budgetary squeeze will also necessitate lower spending in areas that may invest in and improve the economy, like education or infrastructure.

Figure 7 (repeated) – Source: IPSS (2021)

Japan also suffers from a lack of internal investment due to demographic challenges (D'Ambrogio, 2020). As outlined previously, Japanese firms are less profitable than they could be due to the limited workforce pushing up the cost of labour, and are therefore less attractive to investors, with investments providing lower returns. Furthermore, Japanese banks are struggling to adapt to these demographic challenges. They have been reluctant to provide services catered to the growing elderly population, partially because of the risk of scamming (D'Ambrogio, 2020). As the elderly hold many financial assets and are typically savers, this stifles investment by reducing the available pool of savings banks have to lend, thus making credit less available in the Japanese economy.

Conclusion

Japan's economic growth has been stubbornly sluggish, despite the best efforts of its government and central bank. Due to the impact of the ageing population weighing on public finances and the economy, it looks set to remain so. Japan will be the test case for an issue that will face many wealthy countries in the coming decades. Perhaps, as with its rapid industrialisation, it will be the first nation to overcome the challenge - or perhaps its demographic issues will force it into economic decline. Only time will tell.

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